

THE IMPORTANCE OF LEARNING COMPONENTS IN DEVELOPING READING AND TEXT COMPREHENSION LITERACY IN PRIMARY STUDENTS

Sh.R. Yarmatov

Independent Researcher of Uzbekistan National Pedagogical University

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Abstract. *This article discusses the content of reading and understanding the text, the need to encourage positive reading in the formation of reading skills in students' first years of school, and provides recommendations for developing good reading skills in primary school students. It also presents components of reading such as phonemic awareness, phonetics, fluency, vocabulary, and comprehension, and expresses subjective attitudes towards them.*

Keywords: *reading, reading skills, reading components, phonemic awareness, phonetics, fluency, vocabulary, comprehension, reading comprehension, vocabulary, synonyms, antonyms.*

Introduction

The latest achievements in improving the methodology for developing reading and text comprehension literacy in primary school students, as well as the methodological features and pedagogical capabilities of effective functional mechanisms, are being intensively introduced into the educational process.

At the educational stages of our republic, in particular, primary school students are being created normative foundations for creative, logical, intellectual, speech, acmeological, accurate, correct speech, literate writing, reading the context and drawing logical conclusions from it. The Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On approval of the Concept for the development of the public education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030” sets the task of “forming students from an early age with a healthy, strong and effective motivation to study and develop the ability to choose a profession, independently plan their professional growth, and master modern professions”[1], which provides for the improvement of teaching methods and the gradual implementation of the principles of individualization in the educational process.

In the explanatory dictionary of active words of the current Uzbek language, the term “Reading” is defined as follows: “reading 1 To read fl. noun. Reading a book. 2 Lesson, lesson. Attending a study” [6].

According to methodologists, reading is a form of speech activity that consists of identifying, actively processing, and understanding information from a text. True, reading a text is identifying the information contained in it. However, this is not its specific description. Because listening to speech in general, understanding what is being told or someone reading aloud is also identifying, actively processing, and understanding information. Therefore, the important feature of reading is not in the receipt of information, but in the basis on which the receipt of information takes place. The reading process is closely related to the text. Even the best reader, when faced with a difficult word or a complex text, begins to read slowly with difficulty[9].

Foreign scholars, in their research on the learning of primary school students, define the concept of “Reading” as follows: “Reading is the basis of academic success, an important sign of a person’s personal and professional skills”[3].

In his scientific article, L. Fiester, while focusing on the reading skills of 3rd grade students, emphasizes that "having good reading skills in the third grade is very important for a student to achieve success in the future, and that by this time the student has moved from good reading skills on topics in school textbooks to the use of critical reading skills" [4].

Studies by D. Guinness and other foreign scholars emphasize that "the main components of reading are vocabulary, reading the text, and understanding it"[5].

S. Barr, Z. Eslami, R.M. Joshi give the following recommendations for developing good reading skills in students:

- "identify the relationships between new and familiar words;
- find the meaning of unfamiliar words in dictionaries;
- analyze synonyms and antonyms;
- analyze the grammatical structure of words (affixes, compound words, abbreviations);
- work on the meaning of new words collectively and individually"[2].

Foreign researcher Smith, analyzing the attitudes toward reading of elementary and high school students, emphasizes that "developing a positive attitude toward reading is important" [10]. He also studies the regression correlation between the attitudes toward reading of 1st graders and 6th-9th-12th graders and concludes that "given that 1st graders have low reading performance when they enter school, their attitudes toward reading improve later, and their reading performance deteriorates again in high school, it is necessary to focus on developing relatively consistent and positive reading over time" [10].

"At the beginning, middle, and end of the learning process, learners use a combination of language skills, cognitive and metacognitive strategies, and a set of primary knowledge and skills to shape content. In the learning process, elementary school students build on their acquired language-level units, learning-knowledge, and cognitive skills"[8].

Researcher Jill Wright[7] in her dissertation distinguished the following components of learning:

Analyzing each of these component elements separately will help elementary school students develop their reading skills, read the text, and draw conclusions from it.

As we know, phonetics is a branch of linguistics that studies the methods of formation and acoustic properties of speech sounds; syllables, parts of speech separated by pauses. Correct pronunciation of speech sounds is important for students to develop the skill of reading correctly. Along with phonetics, phonemic awareness is also important in developing students' reading literacy and forming the ability to read and understand the text.

Fluency is defined as the ability to read text and refers to reading quickly and accurately.

Comprehension is the emergence of cognitive activity based on the semantics of the context of the reader. D. Ginnis and other foreign scholars emphasize in their studies that "the main components of reading are vocabulary, reading the text, and understanding it"[5].

A dictionary is a source of expression for a primary school student, a collection of words that exist in a particular language. A dictionary can also be called vocabulary. A student's vocabulary is reflected in his ability to understand the text and express his conclusions based on independent thinking. A word is the smallest meaningful unit of language. A student's vocabulary is increased by working with a dictionary and is effective in developing his thinking, expanding his worldview, and acquiring the ability to think logically and creatively.

Conclusion. In conclusion, it should be noted that improving the quality and efficiency of education through integrative, communicative, and innovative approaches to reading, speaking, and writing is one of the urgent tasks of today. Reading components are of great importance and are considered to be the main factors in developing reading and text comprehension literacy in primary school students.

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